

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15547273

Tax Incentives and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of tax incentive on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Nigeria from the periods of 1995-2024. Given the significance of FDI to economic growth and the use of tax incentives as a strategy among government of various countries to attract FDI, this study examines the impact of tax incentives in the decision of an investor to locate FDI in Nigeria. Export expansion grant and Gas utilization incentive were chosen as variables for the study. Data were drawn from annual statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria and the World Bank World Development Indicators Database. The work employs a model of multiple regressions using static Error Correction Modelling (ECM) technique to determine the time series properties of tax incentives captured by annual tax revenue as a percentage of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and FDI. According to the findings of this research, the tax incentives in Nigeria have a beneficial impact on the foreign direct investment in the country. The results showed that an increase or decrease in the tax incentive variables has a significant effect on the foreign direct investment in Nigeria. A combined management of export expansion grants and gas utilization incentive has a significant effect on the foreign direct investment in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends among others that the application and approval processes for the export expansion grant and GUI should be more simplified, transparent and clearly defined. The accelerated tax incentive should be targeted at industries that have high potential for growth and job creation, such as renewable energy, information technology, or healthcare.

Keynote: Tax Incentives, Foreign Direct Investment, Export Expansion Grant, Gas Utilization Incentives

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Taxation is an important tool of fiscal policy of any country. It serves as an instrument for the direction and control of economic activities and enhancement of the people's standard of living. Taxation is the imposition of compulsory levies on the individuals and entities by governments for the purpose of raising revenue for government expenditure and economic development. Taxation can be used to promote investment in some sectors such as mining, manufacturing, agriculture and other small and medium enterprises which are believed to have significant impact on the fiscal wellbeing of the country especially in the area of employment generation and export (Ekwunife, Emuveyan & Nduka, 2021). Foreign direct investments refers to capital movements in the form of investments made to acquire lasting interest in enterprises operating outside of the economy of the investor (UNCTAD, 2007) and are viewed as the engine of economic growth as it provides the needed capital for investment, raise competition in the host country industries, creates employment opportunities, protects environmental and social responsibility, and aids indigenous firms to be more productive, by employing more efficient technology or by investing in human and/or physical capital (Peters & Kiabel, 2015). Prior studies have tried to establish impact of

tax incentives on FDI (Emuveyan, Egungwu, & Joseph, 2023; Manasseh, Chine, Okanya, Nduka, Ede, Okeke, Lawal, & Ugwu, 2025; Igbu, & Ofor, 2021). Their argument is that the tax policy in place can encourage or discourage FDIs. They observed that the attractiveness of a country to foreign investors is higher when it has low and well-harnessed tax policies in place to stimulate the inflow of FDIs. The problem of multiple taxes, complex tax rates, unfriendly environment, weak regulations and the fact that the revenue collected from taxes may not have been used to provide the infrastructural facilities, may obstruct the inflow of FDIs (Gondor & Nistor, 2012). Furthermore, Munongo (2015) and Monogbe, Nduka and Nerdam (2016) observed that taxation may affect FDI in two ways. On one hand, it can reduce the average income of an investment project, influencing the decisions of internationalization and localization of companies. On the other hand, it can influence investment decision by changing the cost of the companies' capital.

With the dwindling revenue base in recent times, foreign capital from FDIs is much needed to aid the government in achieving its developmental goals. One of the strategies employed by governments to achieve this goal is the provision of tax incentives. The Nigerian government in recognition of the importance of FDI as an important medium for industrial progress has readily entered into bilateral agreement with foreign governments, or private organizations that wish to invest in the country as well as discuss the additional incentives (Nduka, Nwankwor, & Egungwu, (2024). Tax incentive, according to international monetary fund (IMF) is provisions in the tax law that allows taxpayers to reduce their tax liability, often in exchange for undertaking specific activities or investments. (IMF, 2019). However, despite the provision of tax incentives, Nigeria's FDI inflows have remained relatively low compared to other African countries (UNCTAD, 2020). As a matter of fact, between 2020 and 2023, many foreign investors left Nigeria, either by transferring ownership, selling their stakes or scaling down operations. The most recent is the sale of beverage company Diageo's 58.02 per cent shareholding in Guinness Nigeria to Tolaram Group on June 11, 2024. Idowu and Awe (2014) investigated the major determinants of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows in Nigeria and reported that FDI inflows into Nigeria have been relatively low due to factors such as high inflation rates, lack of openness, poor economic growth, frequent political instability, insecurity, inadequate infrastructure, and pervasive corruption. While Nduka, Anochie and Egungwu (2024); Alade and Elosiuba (2024) reported negative effect, Olaleye, Riro and Memba (2016), Abdioglu et al (2016), Kyari (2020); Igbu, Ukachi, and Ike (2024); Akam, Ohaka and Ikegwu (2023) reported positive influence of tax incentives on FDI. Still, Raphael and Ofonime (2019); Nduka, Atueyi, Osakwe and Mbanefo (2021) reported no effect and mixed results respectively. "Any incentive to be granted should be broad, sector-based, tenured and transparent; Implementation should be properly monitored, evaluated, periodically reported and kept under review; Revenue forgone from tax incentives or concessions should be quantified against expected benefits and reported annually. Where the benefits cannot be quantified, qualitative factors must be considered; and tax policies on investments should not promote monopoly such as entry barriers or otherwise prevent competition." The broad objective of this study is to analyze the impact of tax incentives on foreign direct investment in Nigeria. The following are the specific objectives that will guide the study: To examine the impact of Export Expansion Grant (EEG) scheme and Gas Utilization Incentive on foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria. The decreasing FDI inflows in Nigeria despite the various tax incentives' provisions have raised questions on the effectiveness of the various tax incentives' provisions in Nigeria. Therefore, this study was carried out to investigate the impact of tax incentives on FDI in Nigeria from 1995 to 2024. Against the above background of the study the following null hypothesis guides the study:

H₀₁: Export expansion grant (EEG) scheme has no significant impact on foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Gas Utilization Incentive has no significant impact on foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Foreign Direct Investment

Foreign direct investment is a category of cross-border investment in which an investor resident in one country establishes a lasting interest with significant degree of influence over an enterprise resident in another economy. According to Ndagi (2016) and Nduka, Ananwude and Osakwe (2019), FDI is when a foreign investor acquires at least 10% of the shareholding and voting rights of a foreign company. This point adds insight to the question of managing ownership. The purchase of a minimum shareholding share of 10% is considered to be considerable and this makes the international investor a long-term management stake in the investor.

FDI is viewed as the commitment of funds, resources, technology and skill in an enterprise, resident in another country, made to acquire a lasting interest and maximizes profit in enterprises operating outside of the economy of the investor. Looking at it from the development context, FDI is viewed as an essential catalyst to the economic growth of developing countries. This follows from the fact that FDI has been found to increase technology and capital transfers, boost employment generation, and improve the economic conditions of host countries.

Export Expansion Grant (EEG) scheme:

The export expansion grant scheme grants the export credit certificate (ECC) as an incentive that can be used to settle all federal government taxes, such as VAT, WHT, CIT, etc. it can be used to purchase government bonds and debts due to the Assets Management Company of Nigeria (AMCON). It aims to support active exporters, expanding their international businesses through a post-shipment incentive designed to encourage Nigerian exporters to expand their export volume and value and improve the global competitiveness of Nigerian products.

The Scheme operates the “weighted eligibility criteria” in assessing applications for EEG. The baseline data as supplied by individual applicant company is used in its assessment. Thus the method of assessment is “company cum product specific.” A company’s EEG assessment is conducted once yearly and the determined rate applies throughout the year. The weighted eligibility criteria have four bands: 15%, 10%, 7.5% and 5%.

Gas Utilization Incentives

The gas utilization incentive is a tax incentive granted to companies engaged in trade or business of gas utilization in Nigeria. This incentive is aimed at encouraging companies to invest in gas utilization projects, which can help reduce the gas flaring and increase the country’s energy production. The incentive can be claimed as an allowance against the company’s taxable income, which can help reduce their tax liability. Investors in gas pipelines can obtain an additional tax-free period of five years. On 28 February 2024, his Excellency, President Bola Ahmed Tinubu, GCFR, signed three Executive Orders as part of the Federal Government of Nigeria’s commitment to improve the investment climate and position Nigeria as the preferred investment destination for the petroleum sector in Africa. The executive Orders became effective 28 February 2024. Under one of the Orders, the oil and Gas Companies (Tax Incentives, Exemption, Remission, etc) Order 2024, a gas company shall be granted a 25% investment allowance on actual qualifying expenditure on plant and equipment incurred on any new and ongoing project. The allowance shall be granted as an allowable deduction from the assessable profit of the company from the year of purchase of the relevant plant and equipment. The allowance shall not be considered in ascertaining the residue of qualifying expenditure incurred on such plant and equipment. A company shall only be granted the allowance upon the expiration of the tax-free period granted under section 39(1) of the Companies Income Tax Act.

Theoretical Framework

The study is underpinning on tax competition theory.

Tax Competition Theory

Tax competition in simple terms, means a choice by a government as to what taxes to levy, in what amounts, and on whom. It is a form of regulatory competition which exists when governments use reductions to encourage the inflow of productive resources or to discourage the exodus of those resources. Often, this means a government strategy of attracting foreign direct investment, (financial investment), and high value human resources by minimizing the overall taxation level and/or special tax preferences, creating a comparative advantage.

This theory was proposed by Oats in 1972 and proposes that in order to encourage the inflow of valuable resources and reduce the outflow of production resources, governments deliberately reduce economic burdens. Therefore, Kiburi, Mirie, Okiro, and Ruigu (2017) suggests that the tax competition theory may be used to understand governments efforts to reduce economic burdens in order to bring in more foreign investments such as skilled and qualified human capital and financial investments into the country. Consequently, this theory suggests that in ensuring that enough foreign direct investments are attracted to a country, the governments try to ensure that their tax policies in place in terms of the tax rates and the taxes collected from foreign investments are favorable enough to attract new and retain the existing foreign investments in the country.

Empirical Review

Alade and Elosiuba (2024) examined the influence of tax incentives on Foreign Direct Investments in Nigeria. This study adopted an ex-post facto research design and data was gathered from CBN statistical bulletin and annual reports of the Federal Inland Revenue Service for the period of 33 years (1991 to 2023). The E - Views 11.0 econometric software was used to analyze the data that was gathered from the various sources. The results revealed a significant negative impact of Customs and Excise Duties (CED) Incentive on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) underscores the importance of streamlining administrative processes to reduce the complexities and burdens these incentives may impose on investors. Conversely, the insignificant impacts of Value Added Tax (VAT) Incentives petroleum profit tax (PPT)) and Company Income Tax (CIT) Incentives suggest that these measures alone are insufficient to drive FDI, thereby highlighting the necessity of a holistic approach that integrates these incentives with broader economic strategies. The authors recommended, among others, that, a simplified customs procedure to mitigate perceived complexities and enhance the attractiveness of these incentives to potential investors. Similarly, Oyerogba et al (2024) investigated the relationship between tax incentives and the inflow of foreign direct investment into listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria and contributes to the literature on the effectiveness of tax incentives in economic growth. They analyzed a survey response from 296 respondents purposively drawn among the relevant stakeholders in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The survey data were analyzed together with secondary data from 65 listed manufacturing firms from 2012 to 2021 using an unbalanced panel regression analysis method. The results establish a significant relationship between tax incentives and foreign direct investment for all the three tax incentives categories. The robustness check analysis also established that apart from firm age, all firm-specific variables have a significant influence on foreign direct investment, indicating that tax incentive cannot drive massive investments in the manufacturing sector. The results underscore the importance of equipping regulatory authorities and policymakers with a comprehensive understanding of the influences of tax incentives, non-tax incentives and other firm-specific variables on foreign direct investment. We posit that eliminating routine redundancy associated with the administration of tax incentives is to attract foreign funding to grow manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Akinyemi et al. (2024) investigates the impact of tax incentives, specifically rural investment allowances and pioneer status, on compliance among listed food and beverage firms in Nigeria. Using regression analysis, we found that rural investment allowances significantly enhance compliance, explaining 97.8% of the variance, while pioneer status shows a non-significant impact. The findings highlight the

importance of targeted tax incentives in promoting regulatory adherence and economic development. Recommendations include enhancing rural investment allowance programs, leveraging incentives for operational efficiency, and reevaluating the pioneer status framework to ensure effectiveness in encouraging compliance and investment. These insights offer valuable guidance for policymakers and businesses.

Terence, Ngala and Mungai (2024) assessed the impact of tax incentives on foreign direct investment inflow in Kenya from 2002-2021. The Q-Theory of Investment and tax competition theory guided the study. Descriptive, correlation, and causal research designs were used for the study employing time series data. The data for the trend in FDI inflow was derived from World Investment Reports, World Bank, and IMF. The results showed that tax incentives ($t=4.811738$, $p<0.05$) and government recurrent expenditure ($t=2.402518$, $p<0.05$) had a positive significant effect on FDI Inflow while government external debt ($t=-3154145$, $p<0.05$) had a negative effect on FDI inflow in Kenya. To enhance the inflow of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), the research suggested that policymakers should strategically optimize tax incentives, including Corporate Income Tax (CIT).

Nwankwo, Nduka and Arinze (2023) an appraisal of the pioneer status incentive on investment in Nigeria visa-vis the recent amendment in the tax laws on this subject. The findings review that the pioneer status incentive gives a competitive edge to the eligible companies over their counterparts that are not enjoying the incentive. This may enable them to reduce their costs, increase their profits, reinvest in their businesses, expand their operations, improve their products and services, and gain more market share. The incentive may also attract more foreign direct investment and technology transfer to Nigeria, which may enhance the capacity and efficiency of the local industries.

Uthman (2023) analyzed the legal framework for the grant of pioneer status incentive and identify its impacts on promotion of investment in Nigeria. Loopholes in the provisions of the law that governs the grant of PSI were identified, and recommendations to the major findings were subsequently made. To arrive at the above aims, doctrinal method was employed. Thus, the provisions of IDITRA and other subsidiary legislations related to it were carefully examined. It was found that from 2017 to 2020, the PSI attracted N15, 153, 970.64. A total number of 21,917 employments were generated from the companies. It was also found that the attitude of some officials in charge of processing and granting the incentives equally found that the provisions of the Act on penalties against the offences perpetrated under the Act were inadequate. It was therefore recommended that any official involved in a proven act of corruption must be prosecuted and the provisions of IDITRA on penalties should be amended.

Olowo, Anisere-Hammed and Adewole (2020) examined the influence of tax incentives on the growth and development of Manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The authors employed ex-post facto research design. Data on corporate income tax incentives, capital allowance incentives, custom duty incentives, excise tax incentives and return on asset were secondarily sourced from financial statement of account from 2013 to 2018. The data were analysed using ordinary least square of multiple regression technique through E-view 9.0. Based on the analysis of the study, the findings show that corporate income tax incentives ($P = 0.00 < 0.05$) has positive and significant effect on return on asset; capital allowance incentives ($P = 0.00 < 0.05$) has positive and significant effect on return on asset; custom duty incentives ($P = 0.00 < 0.05$) has positive and significant effect on return on asset, excise tax incentives ($P = 0.00 < 0.05$) has positive and significant effect on return on asset in Nigeria. The study concluded from findings of the study that tax incentives on the growth and development of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study recommended the need for the government to conduct cost benefit analyses in order to ensure that the goals of granting such incentives are achieved.

Kinyua and Wanjala (2020) conducted a study aimed to find how tax incentive affects the foreign direct investment by paying attention to the East African Community bloc. The use of tax incentives has tremendously grown since the early 90's due to globalization and creation of common markets through regional integration. The logic behind granting tax incentives is to offer potential enterprises opportunities to invest where taxes are seen as impediments. Tax incentives are meant to foster investments into particular economic sectors or industries that are identified as crucial areas of development. The study

used the random effect panel model to carry out this investigation. The study concludes that Tax incentive significantly affects foreign direct investment in the East African Community.

Adenugba and Dipo (2017) studied Non-oil exports and the economic growth of Nigeria: A study of agricultural and mineral resources. The study evaluated the performance of Nigeria’s export promotion strategies as to whether they have been effective in diversifying the productive base of the Nigerian Economy from Crude oil as the major source of foreign exchange. The study was carried out for the period 1981 to 2010. Findings from the study revealed that non– oil exports have performed below expectations giving reason to doubt the effectiveness of the export promotion strategies that have been adopted in the Nigerian Economy. The study revealed that the Nigerian Economy is still far from diversifying from crude oil export and as such the crude oil sub– sector continues to be the single most important sector of the economy. The study made some recommendations for diversification to be achieved and for enhancing the productivity and output of non–oil commodities as well as providing markets for the commodities. Unit root test was not conducted before the estimation. This may undermine the result.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Ex-post facto research design was used in the study. The choice of this research design was made because it deals with time series data. The population of the study consists of all the data on the selected tax incentives in Nigeria from 1995 to 2024. Data collected were analyzed using the ordinary least square regression model (OLS), with the help of E – views 8.0 software application.

Model Specification

Based on Edo et al.’s (2020) model which was adopted and modified to suit the objectives of this study as expressed below:

$$FDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1LFDI + \beta_2LLEG + \beta_3GUI + \beta_4EXT + \beta_5INFL + \mu \dots \dots \text{Eqn (1)}$$

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics

	LFDI	LLEG	LGUI	EXCH	INFL
Mean	9.556415	5.930537	5.115124	56.13000	21.92667
Median	10.05240	6.739901	5.295661	21.89000	15.00000
Maximum	12.91409	9.248378	5.751238	150.8800	72.80000
Minimum	5.314191	2.014903	3.909018	0.610000	5.400000
Std. Dev.	2.326042	2.518503	0.476837	58.27995	17.62729
Skewness	-0.289210	-0.273893	-0.739679	0.458472	1.378337
Kurtosis	1.985858	1.665988	2.512894	1.387912	3.978644
Jarque-Bera	1.703816	2.599574	3.032213	4.299516	10.69625
Probability	0.426600	0.272590	0.219565	0.116512	0.004757
Sum	286.6924	177.9161	153.4537	1683.900	657.8000
Sum Sq. Dev.	156.9037	183.9428	6.593834	98500.03	9010.919
Observations	30	30	30	30	30

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

The table above indicates that the mean of foreign direct investment (FDI) is 9.55 with standard deviation of 2.32, the minimum and maximum values of 5.31 and 12.91 respectively. The mean export expansion grant (EEG) is 5.93 with standard deviation of 2.51 the minimum and maximum values of 2.01 and 9.24 respectively. The mean value of gas utilization incentive (GUI) is 5.11 with standard deviation of 0.47, the minimum and maximum values of 3.90 and 5.75 respectively. Exchange rate (EXCH) mean value is 56.13 with standard deviation of 58.25, the minimum and maximum values of 0.61 and 150.88

respectively. The mean value of inflation (INF) mean value is at 21.9 with standard deviation of 17.62, the minimum and maximum values of 5.40 and 72.80 respectively.

These results suggest that the data are not widely dispersed from the mean because the standard deviations of all the variables are less than the mean values. Also, the skewness value of all the variables is close to zero except exchange rate, it means that the distribution of the variables is symmetric in nature. The Kurtosis values of all the variables is also closer to 3, except FDI, EXCH and EEG it indicates that the shape is a normal distribution. The P-value of Jarque-Bera test of all the variables is more than 5%. However, Shao (2003) submits that normality of data does not in any way affect the inferential statistics estimate to the BLUE.

Correlation Test

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	LFDI	LEEG	LGUI	EXCH	INFL
LFDI	1.000000				
LEEG	0.471316	1.000000			
LGUI	-0.131338	-0.196596	1.000000		
EXCH	0.473154	0.373020	-0.364489	1.000000	
INFL	-0.118618	-0.118799	0.248055	-0.301227	1.000000

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

Table 2 above presents the correlation matrix of the independents variables. There is no correlation coefficient greater than 0.8, hence there is no problem of multicollinearity of data. Therefore, in checking for multicollinearity problem, the study noticed from the correlation table above that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated and thereby ruled out the case of having an outlier. This indicates the absence of multi-collinearity problem in the model used for the analysis.

Unit Root Test

It is necessary to verify the stationary properties of the variables in order to determine their order of integration. The ADF unit root test has been carried out on levels and differences of relevant variables. Each variable is tested for a unit root by employing the dickey –fuller approach with an intercept term. The null hypothesis underlying the unit root is that the variables under investigation have no unit root, while the alternative hypothesis is that it does. The table below shows the stationary properties of the variables.

Table 3: Unit Root Result

Variables	ADF	Integration	Significance
FDI	-6.459298	1(1)	1%
EEG	-5.930234	1(1)	1%
GUI	-5.486535	1(1)	1%
EXCH	-5.025611	1(1)	1%
INFL	-5.196854	1(1)	1%

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

From the result in table 3 above, it is well observed that foreign direct investment is integrated at level 1(1), furthermore, Export Expansion Grant (EEG), Gas Utilization Incentive (GUI), Exchange Rate (EXCH) and Inflation Rate (INFL) were all integrated at first difference 1(1). This implies that all the variables are stationary at level, first differencing with ADF values are higher than their critical values at 1%, 5% and 10% significance level. More so, because of the differences in the order of integration the research conducted bound test for co-integration.

Co-integration Analysis

The aim of co-integration analysis is to determine the long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables. In the Engle-granger co integration analysis, variables of consideration are said to be co integrated or have a long-run equilibrium relationship if in the OLS regression of one variable on the others. Co-integration exists among the variables if they are integrated of the same order. The implication

of this analysis is that deviation or drift may occur between the variables but this is temporary as equilibrium hold in the long run for them. In this study we used the Johansen co-integration approach to examine the existence of long-run relationship between the variables of interest. Below is the summary of co integration result.

Table 4: Co-integration result test

Unrestricted Co-integration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace static	0.05 critical value	Prob**
None *	0.890708	189.2388	125.6154	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.816777	127.2544	95.75366	0.0001
At most 2 *	0.759946	79.73699	69.81889	0.0066
At most 3	0.218544	8.434557	15.49471	0.4202
At most 4	0.053171	1.529839	3.841466	0.2161

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Trace test indicates 3 co-integrating equ(s) as the 0.05 level* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level **mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) P – values.

Unrestricted co-integration Rank Test (Maximum Eigen value)

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigen value	Trace static	0.05 critical value	Prob
None *	0.890708	61.98438	46.23142	0.0005
At most 1 *	0.816777	47.51744	40.07757	0.0061
At most 2 *	0.759946	39.95295	33.87687	0.0083
At most 3	0.218544	6.904717	14.26460	0.5005
At most 4	0.053171	1.529839	3.841466	0.2161

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

Max-Eigen value test indicates 3 co-integrating equations at the 0.5 level* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level **mackinnon-Haug-michelis (1999) P-values.

Trace test value and Max-Eigen indicates 4 co-integrating equations at the 0.05 level. This suggests a long run equilibrium relationship among the variables. Co-integration is a pre-requisite for error correction mechanism following the result of co-integration, there is a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variable, hence, we can move over to error correction mechanism.

Table 5: Error Correction Model Result

Dependent Variable: LFDI
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 03/17/25 Time: 04:01
 Sample: 1995 2024
 Included observations: 30

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.426253	2.739453	2.345816	0.0280
LEEG	0.495525	0.243679	2.033512	0.0537
LGUI	0.899794	0.335107	2.685096	0.0132
EXCH	0.011408	0.005243	2.175812	0.0401
INFL	-0.300882	0.006149	-0.143380	0.8872
ECM(1)	-0.112681	0.266994	-3.422037	0.6773
R-squared	0.759535	Mean dependent var		9.556415
Adjusted R-squared	0.748979	S.D. dependent var		2.326042
S.E. of regression	0.525404	Akaike info criterion		1.751663
Sum squared resid	6.349124	Schwarz criterion		2.078609
Log likelihood	-19.27495	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.856256
F-statistic	90.89853	Durbin-Watson stat		1.634233
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

A regression line intercept of 6.426253 is displayed in the result in table 4.5, with a p-value of 0.0280, which is less than 0.05, the t-test result is 2.345816, which is positive and statistically significant. This suggests that when there is no change in the explanatory variables, that foreign direct investment will remain constant at 6.0% per cent annually. Regression result demonstrates a statistically significant positive correlation between export expansion grant and foreign direct investment. Export expansion grant rate have a value 0.495525, which suggests that a 4% decrease in export expansion grant will, ceteris paribus, result in a 4% increase in foreign direct investment. This is in line with the apriori prediction. This finding bolsters the theory that raising Export expansion grant will increase foreign direct investment. There is a positive relationship between gas utilization incentive and foreign direct investment. The exchange rate value is 0.899794. This suggests that a one percent increase in the gas utilization incentive will, ceteris paribus, result in an increase in foreign direct investment by roughly 8 percent. This is in line with the apriori prediction. This finding corroborates the theory that increase in gas utilization incentive will increases the foreign direct investment. There is a positive relationship between exchange rate and foreign direct investment. The value of exchange rate is 0.011408, which suggests that a 1% increase foreign direct investment, ceteris paribus, result in a 1% increase in exchange rate. This is in line with the apriori prediction. This finding confirms that increases in exchange rate increases the foreign direct investment in Nigeria. There is negative relationship between inflation rate and foreign direct investment. The value of inflation rate is -0.300882, which suggests that a 3% decrease in inflation rate will, ceteris paribus, result in a 3% increase in foreign direct investment. This is in line with the apriori prediction. This finding confirms that decreases in inflation rate increases the foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: Export expansion grant has no significant impact on foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

From the result report of our t-test in table 4.3 above, it was observed from the result that the value of export expansion grant is 2.033512 with the probability of 0.0537 which is within the desired level of significant (0.05), we therefore reject null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that export expansion grant has significant effect on foreign direct investment.

H₀₂: Gas utilization incentive has no significant impact on foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

From the forgoing result we find out that computed value for Gas utilization incentive is 2.685096 while it's probability is 0.0132 this shows that the gas utilization incentive is statistically significant. Based on this analysis we reject (H₀) and accept (H₁), which implies that gas utilization incentive has a significant effect on foreign direct investment in Nigeria.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the above findings it is concluded that foreign direct investments' enjoying tax incentives will generate more employment opportunities than firms in highly taxed regions. Conducive investment climate is a strong requirement for the flow of sustainable physical investment in the economy. Tax incentives positively influence the foreign direct investment and expand variety of goods available to consumers.

The following recommendation was made:

1. The policy makers should enhance the export expansion grant scheme and strategically optimize the incentive so as to improve/increase the flow of foreign direct investment into Nigeria.
2. The use of GUI should be encouraged and optimized as increase in the GUI leads to increase in the inflow of FDI into Nigeria. This can be done by making sure that the approval process for the GUI is streamlined and simplified, with clear guidelines and timeframes to ensure that eligible projects can access the incentive in a timely manner.

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